

SHAPING ECOSYSTEMS AND BEYOND BANKS

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Annotation: *This article describes shaping ecosystems and beyond banks. People who are not close to this field may think that these two are different fields. If we understand the essence of these areas, we will certainly find important aspects of each other. Throughout the article, you can learn clear and analytical information about both of these areas.*

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It is natural to expect that a well-designed digital bank will become the basis of a much larger financial ecosystem or even a set of interconnected ecosystems. As important components of such an ecosystem, digital service providers can be considered as insurers, brokers, wealth managers, roboadvisors, credit card issuers, cross-border payment providers, currency exchanges and P2P lenders. The ability of these companies to meet the financial needs of their customers will be significantly improved as they enter a broader financial system through digital banking. At the same time, the bank benefits by gaining additional information about customers' requirements and habits, thus closing the information-related communication chain. Customers should be provided with appropriate privacy guarantees.

In addition, the digital cash issued by the bank can serve as a lubricant, allowing the trading wheels to rotate faster and more efficiently than is currently possible. One can imagine DBF in the center of the Internet of Things, which can be considered a bank of things. For example, if a bank customer notifies him that the

roof needs to be repaired, the bank can immediately recommend several contractors, arrange offers, help the customer choose the most suitable one, and arrange for its financing. Thus, in addition to the financial business, DBF can include a variety of non-financial participants in its ecosystem. All of these developments will increase the social utility of the bank and its appreciation by the public, while at the same time increasing its profitability. Banks need to keep in mind that there is no time to lose, as the competition for current digital champions for their customers' digital wallets will be fierce from Google, Amazon, Facebook and Alibaba.

The unsatisfactory state of affairs with existing banks offers a unique opportunity to build a digital bank from scratch. Such a bank carries out its mission through the use of the most advanced technologies, including cryptography and distributed notebook techniques, AI, big data and in-depth study. From the very beginning, it is based on optimizing balance; placement of digital, distributed notebook-inspired infrastructure; and comprehensive automation and digitization of the middle and back office, as well as enhanced security using the most advanced cryptographic methods throughout the organization. By design, this bank will be highly efficient, profitable and fast. And its infrastructure will be flexible enough to work with private digital currencies (e.g. bitcoin) and potential state-issued currencies (e.g. Bitcoin). If it wants, this bank will be able to issue digital currency itself. The Bank freely uses artificial intelligence and big data analysis to create an unprecedented customer experience, automate the issuance of personal and small and medium business loans and improve risk management. By design, such a bank is valued by investors, customers and regulators.

And yet, by building such a bank, have we fallen into the trap of the old paradigm? If you look at WeChat or Sesame and say nothing about the fears of leading telecommunications companies, you will see that even leading companies like Facebook and Google are intimidated by the C-level. Surprisingly, many legacy banks seem more reliable. WeChat is redefining what financial services mean in relation to a wider range of consumer services that attract individuals.

The key is to have customer-oriented information in all areas of life that is stored in a standard format with a standard API that works not only in the corner of financial services or products, but in the entire digital ecosystem. (So it's like a universal PDS, but customers don't own or manage the data; PDS does.) Using this central, panoptic data, WeChat offers life opportunities (e.g., entertainment, business, finance, family) smooth and consistent.

It provides customers with fully integrated payments, credit and banking services, incredible consulting capabilities and excellent KYC / AML, all in a completely transparent manner. Users simply go online and in person, find interesting things, and buy, sell, and trade without problems. WeChat and Sesame also combine health, lifestyle and employment services with money services, making it completely transparent without separate apps or websites. Consumers can only care about things that help them live a better life. However, this depends on the ability of consumers to provide credit when needed. Given the somewhat uncertain and limited capabilities of P2P networks to lend, digital banks need to come to the rescue.

A similar future is emerging for SMEs: customers are shepherding their purchases and there are almost no cash flow issues such as loans, payments and KYC / AML. In the first months of its operation, WeChat reportedly reached more than 1 million SMEs integrated into its services.

Is there a "no banking" future for digital banking? Instead of running digital banking as a separate service, banking functions are invisibly integrated everywhere. There are several urgent problems with this model:

1. Make money. Due to the exclusive and unique role of banks in the creation of loan money, non-bank entities do not have the necessary capacity to meet the financial needs of their customers.

2. Normative restrictions. There are many restrictions on offering banking services to companies in Western Europe and the United States. If China begins to adopt more restrictive financial regulations to better protect consumers, these

regulations will create a less hospitable business environment for these types of services.

3. Securities market pressure. Does WeChat (or the next WeChat) want to expand its high-tech stock market and load it up with discounts for financial services? The more successful you are in financial services, the more acute the question becomes. However, if the technology company is funded intentionally and dimensionally, it can increase shareholder value.

Despite these challenges, is there a model we can call an “invisible bank” that adds to our daily lives without friction? The answer is yes and no - the old banking model will inevitably disappear over time. Some believe that the integration of artificial intelligence into cryptocurrency could pave the way for this invisible banking future (DeFi or decentralized finance); others believe Big Tech like Amazon, Apple, or Ali Baba will make it easier and benefit from it. Nevertheless, in the transition period, digital banks play a role as transaction oils and activators in daily life.

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